

ARDUINO PLATFORM AND IMPLEMENTATION OF MICROELECTRONIC DEVICES USING IT. FIRST OF ALL, LET'S START WITH THE ARDUINO PLATFORM.

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Annotation: Arduino designs, manufactures and supports electronic devices and software that enable people around the world to easily access advanced technologies that interact with the physical world. This platform is simple, straightforward and powerful, ready to meet the needs of users from students to developers and professional developers. It can make it possible to solve all problems through the available electronic and digital technologies.

Keywords: Arduino, design, electronics, community, student, method.

There was once a barrier between the world of electronics, design and programming and the rest of the world. Arduino broke that barrier. Over the years, the platform has been the brains behind thousands of projects, from everyday objects to sophisticated scientific instruments. A worldwide community of students, hobbyists, artists, programmers, and professionals gathers around this open source platform, whose contributions increase the knowledge available to an incredible extent.

The Arduino Team

Founders

Massimo Banzi, Co-founder, CMO & Chairman

Massimo Banzi is an interaction designer, educator, open-source hardware pioneer, and TED speaker. His background is in electrical engineering, but he spent most of his early career working as a software architect before spending four years at the Interaction Design Institute Ivrea as an Associate Professor. He has taught workshops and has been a guest speaker at institutions all over the world.

Always interested in what's new, Massimo started the first FabLab in Italy, and is also the author of the book “Getting Started with Arduino”.

David Cuartielles, Co-founder & FT Content Lead.

David is a university lecturer and leads the Content Unit at Arduino.

He holds an MSc in Telecommunications Engineering and a PhD in Interaction Design, and has lectured at Malmö University in Sweden since 2000. David has been a visiting scholar at universities in the Americas, Europe, and Asia, has written several books on programming, and is an international speaker on open-source hardware and STEAM education.

David has been awarded both for his work at Arduino and his professional career, is an Ashoka Fellow for Spain, and actively supports several SMEs in Spain and the Americas in the field of technology and education.

Tom Igoe

Co-founder

Tom Igoe is the area head for physical computing courses, in which students learn to consider the motivations and actions of the people for whom they're designing as the foundation for physical interaction design. His research interests also include networks, lighting design, the environmental and social impacts of technology development, and monkeys. He has written four books and a number of articles related to electronics and physical interaction.

David Mellis

Co-founder

David A. Mellis is a software architect at Autodesk, building software for circuit design. His work seeks to engage new audiences in using electronics for creative and do-it-yourself practices. Previously, David was a postdoc at UC Berkeley with Björn Hartmann. David completed his graduate studies at the MIT Media Lab, getting his PhD in Mitchel Resnick's Lifelong Kindergarten group and his master's in Leah Buechley's High-Low Tech group.

There are several families of the Arduino platform, which are divided into different classes according to their production and operating principles. One of them is **Classic Family**

In the Classic Family, you will find boards such as the legendary Arduino UNO and other classics such as the Leonardo & Micro. These boards are considered the backbone of the Arduino project, and has been a success for many years.

Boards

- uno
- mega
- leonardo
- uno mini le
- Arduino UNO R3
- Arduino Mega 2560 Rev3
- Arduino Leonardo
- Arduino UNO Mini Limited Edition
- due
- micro
- zero
- uno wifi r2
- Arduino Due
- Arduino Micro

- Arduino Zero
- Arduino UNO WiFi Rev2
- Shields
- motor shield
- 4 relay shield
- ethernet shield
- Arduino Motor Shield Rev3
- Arduino 4 Relay Shield
 - Arduino Ethernet Shield Rev2

We implement a sensor device using a platform belonging to this family. Let's assemble a small device to help Arduino.

Device design

Step 1: Gathering materials

Necessary materials: resistor 221 ohm, 10 wires, 3 leds, 1 arduino uno, 1 working panel, 1 ultrasonic sensor-HC-SR04.

Step 2: Device structure

FIGURE 1

Connect the red wire from the 5V pin of the Arduino to the positive channel of the working board, and the black wire from the GND pin of the Arduino to the negative channel of the working board:

Buzzer = pin 7

Ultrasonic sensor:

Echo = pin 3

Trig = pin 2

LEDs:

RedLED = pin 4

YellowLED = pin 5

GreenLED = pin 6

The green wires connected to the LEDs should be connected to the positive side of the LED, and the negative side of the LED should be connected to the negative channel of the working panel using a 220 ohm resistor.

Step 3: Assembly - Breadboard

We connect the 5V and GND pins of the Arduino to the working board. As I mentioned earlier, we make sure that the wire connected to the 5V pin is connected to the positive channel of the working panel, and the wire connected to the GND pin is connected to the negative channel of the working panel.

Step 4: Assembly - ultrasonic sensor

Time to connect the HC-SRO4 ultrasonic sensor. We need to connect the GND pin on the ultrasonic sensor to the negative channel on the working panel. Then the Trig pin on the sensor is connected to pin 2 on the Arduino and the Echo pin on the sensor is connected to pin 3 on the Arduino and the VCC pin on the ultrasonic sensor is connected to the positive channel on the breadboard.

Step 5: Assembly - LEDs

The next step is to connect the LEDs to the breadboard and the Arduino. Connecting the LEDs is very easy, there is a lot of repetition. Let's attach the green LED first. The way to do this is to connect the anode (longer leg) to pin 6 on the Arduino with a green wire and the cathode (shorter leg) to the negative channel on the breadboard using a 220 ohm. resistance. Then repeat this process for the yellow and red LEDs, connecting the anode (longer leg) of the yellow LED to pin 5 on the Arduino and the anode of the red LED to pin 6.

Step 6: Assembly - Buzzer

The last part of the setup for this is connecting the signal to the breadboard and the Arduino. This is one of the easiest parts of the whole setup. To do this, simply connect the longer leg of the signal to pin 7 of the Arduino using a green wire, and then connect the shorter leg to the negative channel of the breadboard using a 220 ohm resistor. It is recommended to use a resistor when connecting the short leg of the bell to the negative channel of the working panel. This greatly reduces the ringing sound and prevents it from dying out too quickly.

Below you can see a photo of the finished security system dwarf device.

FIGURE 2

In order for the finished device to work, the necessary code is written according to the function of the Arduino's special program and uploaded to the platform. After the program code is loaded, the device will start to work. I will quote this code below.

Program code:

```
#define trigPin 2
#define echoPin 3
#define LEDlampRed 4
#define LEDlampYellow 5
#define LEDlampGreen 6
#define soundbuzzer 7
int sound = 500;
void setup() {
  Serial.begin (9600);
  pinMode(trigPin, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(echoPin, INPUT);
  pinMode(LEDlampRed, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(LEDlampYellow, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(LEDlampGreen, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(soundbuzzer, OUTPUT);
}
void loop() {
  long durationindigit, distanceincm;
  digitalWrite(trigPin, LOW);
  delayMicroseconds(2);
  digitalWrite(trigPin, HIGH);
  delayMicroseconds(10);
  digitalWrite(trigPin, LOW);
  durationindigit = pulseIn(echoPin, HIGH);
  distanceincm = (durationindigit/5) / 29.1;
  if (distanceincm < 50) {
    digitalWrite(LEDlampGreen, HIGH);
  }
  else {
```

```
digitalWrite(LEDlampGreen, LOW);
}
if (distanceincm < 20) {
digitalWrite(LEDlampYellow, HIGH);
}
else {
digitalWrite(LEDlampYellow,LOW);
}
if (distanceincm < 5) {
digitalWrite(LEDlampRed, HIGH);
sound = 1000;
}
else {
digitalWrite(LEDlampRed,LOW);
}
if (distanceincm > 5 || distanceincm <= 0){
Serial.println("Outside the permissible range of distances");
noTone(soundbuzzer);
}
else {
Serial.print(distanceincm);
Serial.println(" cm");
tone(soundbuzzer, sound);
}
delay(300);
}
```

Summary.

This article presents the design and implementation of a microprocessor-based smart electronic measuring device. The proposed device can be used in many security systems. Since the accuracy of the operation of the device is important, we see almost no errors. In addition, software that can be configured with the functions of the smart device; This device provides flexibility for any location.

References

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